

Iodine Trichloride as a Volumetric Reagent. Part II. Determination of Thiourea and its Organic Derivatives

Balwant Singh, Balbir Chand Verma, and M. S. Saran

Iodine trichloride has been used as a volumetric reagent for the determination of thiourea and its many organic alkyl and aryl derivatives both by visual and potentiometric titration methods.

The thioureas are oxidised to disulphides with a single electron-change:

This direct method is simple, accurate, and instantaneous.

Singh and Kashyap¹ used iodine trichloride as a volumetric reagent for the determination of some reducing agents at pH 6.5 to 7.5 in sodium acetate-buffered solutions both by visual and potentiometric methods. No attempt has so far been made to estimate thiourea or its organic derivatives with this reagent.

In the present work iodine trichloride was used as a redox reagent to determine thiourea and some of its alkyl and aryl derivatives in sulphuric acid medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

A known weight (10 to 70 mg.) of each compound was taken in a titration flask. In case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives sufficient water and enough of sulphuric acid were added to keep normality of the solution at 1*N*. Each aryl derivative of thiourea was dissolved in 18*N* sulphuric acid (10 to 15 ml) and sufficient water (40 to 90ml) was added to keep normality of its solution at 3.0 to 3.5*N*. The solution was cooled to room temperature and titrated with standard (*N*/20) iodine trichloride. End point in each case was detected visually as well as potentiometrically. In visual titrations amylose was used as an indicator and the solution acquired a blue colour at the end point. In titrations of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives, chloroform was also used as an indicator which turned pink at the end point.

In potentiometric method, a platinum wire electrode, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode, coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The solution was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer during the titration. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each titration. A series of

1. *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1959, 22, 15.

potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. The potentiometric titrations, one for each compound, are represented by curves A to K in Fig. 1.

From the volume of standard (*N*/20) iodine trichloride solution used corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amount of thiourea or each of its organic derivatives is calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Weight of the compound.

Compounds.	Visual method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken	Found.	Taken.	Found.
NH ₂ .CS.NH ₂	0.0190 g.	0.0190 g.	0.0152 g.	0.0152 g.
	0.0570	0.0568	0.0410	0.0420
CH ₃ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0241	0.0241	0.0202	0.0202
	0.0560	0.0559	0.0440	0.0438
CH ₃ .CH ₂ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0185	0.0185	0.0260	0.0260
	0.0600	0.0601	0.0524	0.0525
(CH ₃) ₂ CH.NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0221	0.0221	0.0115	0.0115
	0.0622	0.0620	0.0648	0.0648
n-CH ₃ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0200	0.0200	0.0119	0.0119
	0.0564	0.0553	0.0530	0.0531
n-CH ₃ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0197	0.0197	0.0207	0.0207
	0.0621	0.0620	0.0539	0.0540
o-(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0318	0.0317	0.0168	0.0168
	0.0649	0.0648	0.0501	0.0501

TABLE I (contd.)

Compounds.	Weight of the compound.			
	Visual method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0195	0.0195	0.0139	0.0139
	0.0538	0.0538	0.0430	0.0430
<i>o</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0180	0.0180	0.0280	0.0280
	0.0690	0.0688	0.0603	0.0604
<i>p</i> -(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0185	0.0185	0.0212	0.0212
	0.0595	0.0596	0.0490	0.0489
<i>o</i> -(OC ₂ H ₅)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0302	0.0302	0.0201	0.0201
	0.0659	0.0659	0.0497	0.0497
<i>p</i> -(OC ₂ H ₅)C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0155	0.0155	..	..
	0.0502	0.0502	..	..
C ₆ H ₅ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0204	0.0204	..	..
	0.0503	0.0503	..	..

The results recorded above show that the listed compounds can be determined by titration with standard (*N*/20) iodine trichloride. Thiourea and its organic derivatives are oxidised by iodine trichloride to their corresponding disulphides:

This direct method is simple, accurate, and instantaneous.